

Draft protocol for a systematic evidence map of methods to measure hormones related to estrogen, androgen and thyroid pathways in fish, birds and amphibians - open peer review

You are kindly invited to comment on a draft systematic evidence mapping protocol aiming to collate literature that addresses the development, optimisation and/or validation of hormone measurement methods in fish, amphibian and bird species.

This draft protocol is now being published on the open repository Zenodo and the main document and appendices can be found here:

<https://zenodo.org/record/2711704#.XNmD8xTdsqM>

This open peer review process will close on 20/05/2019 18:00 (CET).

Participation in this exercise is entirely voluntary and you are free to remain anonymous. You are equally welcome to contact the project team if you have any further comments or would like to be informed of the results by emailing olwenn.martin@brunel.ac.uk.

PIT Statement

In many cases where the search aims to retrieve primary research studies, the review question should be translated into clear and appropriate key elements (i.e. PICO/PECO, PIT, and PO) combined (where necessary or possible) with study design.

Key elements: the components of the review question that specify what information must be provided in a primary study to estimate the parameter under assessment and hence answer the question. The key elements vary depending on the question type: (i) for questions on the effect of an exposure or intervention: PECO/PICO key elements; (ii) for questions on the sensitivity or specificity of a test: PIT key elements; and (iii) for questions on the prevalence of a condition or the incidence of an outcome: PO key elements.

Search concept: a key element which might be used in the search. If the question aims to estimate risk assessment parameters using primary research studies, the search concepts might be one or more of the key elements of the studies that shall be searched (i.e. PICO/PECO, PIT, and PO) and (where possible) the study design. If the question aims to create an inventory of items (e.g. available diagnostic tests for a specific disease) the search concepts are likely to be the disease and the concept of diagnosis (variously expressed).

1. Was the review question clearly defined and translated into correct search concepts?

Mark only one oval.

- Definitely appropriate
- Probably appropriate
- Probably not appropriate
- Definitely not appropriate
- Not applicable

2. Comments:

Search strategy

For each search element, the search should include:

- all possible synonyms (e.g. welfare, wellbeing, etc);
- related terms, e.g. pesticide, pest control, etc.;
- acronyms, e.g. Bluetongue, BTV, etc. If an acronym or abbreviation is used, a full text term or substantial part of a full text term should also be present;
- spelling variants, e.g. behaviour, behaviour; anaemia/anaemia;
- old and new terminology, e.g. aspartame/Phenylalanine;
- brand and generic names, e.g. imidacloprid, Gaucho;
- lay and scientific terminology e.g. aspartame/1-Methyl N-L-alpha-aspartyl-L-phenylalanate;
- common typos (e.g. mitomycin/mitomicin).

In addition, the following aspects should be considered:

- translation issues, which may lead to new translated search terms or to limitations;
- if apparently irrelevant or excessively broad free text terms were used.

You should consider whether:

- “too many” search concepts were used;
- any of the search concepts were too narrow or too broad (Ideally separate searches should be conducted for each considered search concept and then combined.) The process for defining the definitive search should be documented;
- the pilot searches appears to retrieve too many or too few records.
- whether any of the limits used seem unwarranted
- or any potentially helpful limits are missing.

Search filters are pre-tested, and sometimes validated, search strategies which are designed to retrieve specific types of study or topic (such as a specific population) from a named database. They usually consist of a set of indexing and free text terms which describe the study design or topic of interest. The filter is added to the search strategy designed to retrieve the review's key elements, in order to restrict the results to the required study design or topic of interest.

- Are any filters used appropriate for the topic?
- Are any helpful and relevant available filters missing?

3. Were the appropriate search terms (i.e. terms in the title and abstract) identified for each search concept?

Mark only one oval.

- Definitely appropriate
- Probably appropriate
- Probably not appropriate
- Definitely not appropriate
- Not applicable

4. Comments:

5. Is the search string an optimal combination of the search concepts for sensitivity and precision?

Mark only one oval.

- Definitely appropriate
- Probably appropriate
- Probably not appropriate
- Definitely not appropriate
- Not applicable

6. Comments:

7. Were limits appropriately used?

Mark only one oval.

- Definitely appropriate
- Probably appropriate
- Probably not appropriate
- Definitely not appropriate
- Not applicable

8. Comments:

9. Were search filters appropriately used?*Mark only one oval.*

- Definitely appropriate
- Probably appropriate
- Probably not appropriate
- Definitely not appropriate
- Not applicable

10. Comments:

Information sources

More than a single database should be searched. Searches of information sources for different types of publication would help to demonstrate that the search had been extensive:

- Major bibliographic databases (journals and books)
- Information sources recording:
 - o dissertations;
 - o conference reports;
 - o reports;
 - o ongoing research/research registers.

In addition, one or more of the following search techniques should be reported:

- o Manual searches
- o Citation searches
- o Checking websites of relevant organisations

Key studies can be used to check the adequacy of the search strategy when further piloting and refining it.

11. Is the proposed search extensive enough? Will the right (relevant and reliable) combinations of information sources be searched?*Mark only one oval.*

- Definitely appropriate
- Probably appropriate
- Probably not appropriate
- Definitely not appropriate
- Not applicable

12. Comments:

13. **If you are aware of any key papers on the topic that should be captured by the search strategy, please give their references.**

Screening and inclusion criteria

Inclusion and exclusion criteria should be defined in sufficient detail to allow different evaluators to reliably come to the same decision about the eligibility of a given study.

14. **Are the inclusion and exclusion criteria clearly stated? Have any potentially ambiguous studies been anticipated and eligibility in such cases clarified? Are key terms sufficiently well defined?**

Mark only one oval.

- Definitely appropriate
Probably appropriate
Probably not appropriate
Definitely not appropriate
Not applicable

15. **Comments:**

Data extraction and evidence synthesis

16. **Are key variables missing from the data extraction template? Are some variables superfluous? Is the planned data analysis appropriate to answer the study question?**

Mark only one oval.

- Definitely appropriate
Probably appropriate
Probably not appropriate
Definitely not appropriate
Not applicable

17. Comments:

Survey of regulatory laboratories

This analysis will guide the design of a questionnaire addressed to laboratories that routinely carry out regulatory ecotoxicity studies. This questionnaire will seek opinions on technical and scientific aspects as well practical feasibility aspects that are rarely addressed in the scientific literature such as availability of equipment, technical expertise required and costs involved.

18. If you are aware of laboratories routinely carrying regulatory ecotoxicology studies that ought to be included in this survey, please share their affiliation

Thank you!

We are very grateful for the time you took to review this draft protocol. If you like to be sent the the collation of anonymised comments and the revised protocol when made publicly available, feel free to give your email below.

19. email address
